

Kinetics of resin-catalyzed hydrolysis of propionamide in aqueous and nonaqueous media

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Manuscript received 27 June 2002, revised 11 March 2003, accepted 16 April 2003

Rate of hydrolysis of propionamide in the presence of synthetic sulfonated acid resins (H⁺-form) in aqueous and non-aqueous media increases with temperature and with increasing the dielectric constant of the medium. The resin in the Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} or Pb^{II}-form increases the reaction rate more than when in the H⁺-form. Activation parameters have been calculated and discussed. Activation energy (E_a) in different media follows the order : aqueous < glycerol < ethylene glycol < *n*-propanol.

Hydrolysis of amides in the presence of ion exchangers as catalyst has received much less attention than the reaction in homogeneous solution. The resin-catalyzed hydrolysis of amides is controlled by (i) film diffusion, (ii) chemical reaction within the catalyst particles and (iii) chemical reaction at the particle surfaces. Due to factors (i) and (iii), the rate is inversely proportional to the particle size for a given amount of the catalyst. Internal reaction control (ii) is established when the overall rate is independent of the particle size¹ with a given amount of the catalyst. Often, the overall rate is a combination of intraparticle reaction and intraparticle diffusion. The latter can affect the rate but it can never be the sole rate-determining step.

In the present work, we are concerned with the acid hydrolysis of propionamide catalyzed by synthetic organic cation exchange resin, *m*-cresol-phenol-formaldehyde in pure water and to compare the result with those in aqueous glycerol, aqueous ethylene glycol and aqueous *n*-propanol. The other objective was to study the catalytic efficiency of the resin in Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Pb^{II} forms.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows that under the experimental conditions, the values of specific rate constant (k) for propionamide hydrolysis and the % conversion decrease in the order : pure water > glycerol > ethylene glycol > *n*-propanol. It is also

Table 1. Velocity constants and the thermodynamic activation parameters

Medium	Temp. °C	X %	Q	$10^{-5}k$ s^{-1}	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* e.u.	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	
Aqueous	75	60	1.10	8.25	81.43	33.50	137.73		
	83	80	1.07	10.18	82.74	33.41	138.57	36.37	
	90	86	1.02	15.74	83.13	33.35	137.13		
Glycerol	15%	75	54	1.14	6.72	82.04	34.82	135.68	
		83	64	1.13	9.11	83.07	34.73	135.79	37.69
		90	72	1.11	14.30	83.40	34.67	134.24	
	30%	75	50	1.16	3.83	83.70	40.97	122.78	
		83	57	1.15	5.70	84.46	40.88	122.42	43.84
		90	63	1.12	6.60	85.76	40.82	123.80	
	45%	75	39	1.17	2.69	85.63	46.26	113.13	
		83	52	1.15	4.30	85.29	46.17	109.89	49.13
		90	56	1.13	5.20	84.69	46.11	106.28	

Table 1 (contd.)

Ethylene glycol	15%	75	50	1.20	4.80	82.99	36.66	133.13	
		83	61	1.19	7.90	83.51	36.57	131.85	39.53
		90	67	1.17	12.60	83.79	36.51	130.24	
	30%	75	46	1.22	3.26	84.12	42.03	120.94	
		83	53	1.21	4.40	85.23	41.94	121.60	44.90
		90	59	1.20	5.90	86.09	41.88	121.79	
	45%	75	36	1.25	1.92	85.66	48.15	107.78	
		83	47	1.23	2.31	87.03	48.06	109.47	51.02
		90	51	1.22	4.00	87.26	48.00	108.15	
<i>n</i> -Propanol	15%	75	46	1.27	4.22	83.37	37.31	132.35	
		83	57	1.26	5.30	84.69	37.22	133.34	40.18
		90	63	1.24	7.50	85.36	37.16	132.78	
	30%	75	42	1.28	2.90	84.30	43.69	116.69	
		83	50	1.27	4.80	84.96	43.60	116.18	46.56
		90	54	1.25	5.00	86.57	43.54	118.53	
	45%	75	30	1.30	1.34	86.70	52.56	98.10	
		83	35	1.28	1.90	87.71	52.47	98.99	55.43
		90	39	1.26	2.50	88.02	52.41	98.09	

seen that increasing the proportion of any organic solvent in aqueous organic solvents lowers the rate of hydrolysis of the amide and also lowers the percentage of conversion. Thus, from an electrostatic viewpoint, a rate decrease might be expected because of destabilization of the polar transition state when the bulk dielectric constant is lowered by successive addition of the alcohol², since the highly polar transition state is more strongly solvated relative to the less polar ground state.

The results given in Table 2 show that k increases slightly with increasing amount of the acid resin concentration, reaches a maximum value and then falls off at still higher amount of resin. This behavior may be attributed to Benrath conclusions³, the velocity of homogeneous catalytic reaction being the greatest when sufficient acid was added to convert all the amide into a cation. When the acid increased beyond this point, the cation combines with the anion to form an undissociated salt which does not react with water and hence the velocity falls off.

Table 2. Effect of amount of catalyst on the rate constant and percent conversion at 75°

Catalyst {H ⁺ -form}					
Wt., g	5	10	15	20	25
X, %	60	66	70	74	72
10 ⁻⁵ k	8.25	8.97	9.20	9.50	9.40

The Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Pb^{II}-forms of the resin have greater catalytic effect than that in the H⁺-form (Fig. 1). k and % conversion follow the order: Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Pb^{II} > H⁺ (Table 3), suggesting that extensive coordination to the amino group occurs in the complexes of these metal ions which are the best oxygen acceptors in the series^{4,5}.

Fig. 1. Plots for rate constant determination in presence of (a) Zn^{II}, (b) Ni^{II}, (c) Pb^{II} at 75°.

The efficiency of the resin, q , which is the ratio of the reaction rate constants in the heterogeneous system to that with the equivalent amounts of catalyst in homogeneous system, was larger than unity and increased with increasing organic solvent concentration. This means that the ion exchanger is a more effective catalyst than an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid in the process of the

Table 3 Effect of the ion exchange resin in the metal form in equal weights with H⁺ form resin 5 g each 75°

Catalyst {Metal-Form}	H ⁺	Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
X %	60	71	68	66
10 ⁻⁵ k	8.25	10.02	9.91	9.55

propionamide hydrolysis. The decrease of q with temperature is due to the dependence of the sorption effect on the latter.⁶

The data of the effect of temperature on the percent conversion and k are presented in Table 1. The plots of $\log k$ against $1/T$ are practically linear. From the slopes of these lines the energy of activation (E_a) have been calculated⁷ and recorded in Table 1. It is evident that E_a increases noticeably on progressive addition of glycerol, ethylene glycol or *n*-propanol to the reaction medium and then increases slightly in the solvent of high content as $E_{a\text{aqueous}} < E_{a\text{glycerol}} < E_{a\text{ethylene glycol}} < E_{a\text{n-propanol}}$.

It is well known⁸ that the reactants or the activated complexes react with the solvent thereby affecting the rate considerably. The effect of interaction with solvent is to lower the potential energy of the substrate by an amount equal to solvation. If one or both the reactants are more solvated than the activated complex, a decrease in potential energy of the former enhances the activation energy, the reaction rate is consequently diminished. If the activated complex is more solvated than the reactants, the lowering of potential energy causes a decrease in energy of activation of the reaction, the reaction rate is thus increased. On these considerations, the effect of solvent on k and E_a can be understood.⁹

The value of free energy change (ΔG^*) initially increases noticeably with increase in glycerol, ethylene glycol and *n*-propanol content, but slightly with their further addition. The lesser dependence of ΔG^* at higher percentages of organic solvent is due largely to linear compensation between the enthalpy and entropy of activation at a given temperature. According to the theory of absolute reaction rates, an increase in ΔG^* is indicative of the solvation phenomena.¹¹ Therefore, solvation is expected to be more pronounced in the presence of organic solvents studied in the present work.

A major factor governing ΔS^* for reaction in solution is the change in solvation of reactants and transition state, the incorporation of solvent into transition state entails a loss of enthalpy. However, $-\Delta S^*$ values vary with solvent composition in non-linear manner. This behavior indicates specific solvation and hence a non-random distribution of the solvent molecules.^{1,9}

Experimental

Propionamide, *n*-propanol and HCl were purified.¹² All solutions were freshly prepared from analytical grade reagents and standardized. Kinetics measurements were followed by estimating ammonia by standard method^{8,10,11}. The results were reproducible within $\pm 6.0\%$ in the temperature range 75–90° keeping concentration of the propionamide constant. As noted in the acid-catalyzed hydrolysis, kinetics were overall first order reaction.¹¹ The effect of the three organic solvents (glycerol, ethylene glycol and *n*-propanol) was also examined by determining the first order rate constant within the same temperature range. The cation exchange catalyst used was of *m*-cresol-phenol-formaldehyde resin in the H⁺-form, and synthesized as described earlier.¹¹ The different forms of the catalyst in Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Pb^{II} forms were obtained^{5,12} by soaking the resin in mixture solution of 0.01M HCl and 0.01M of the desired metal ions for 24 h and the washed with distilled water to get rid of the metal ions. Water was then removed and dried at 40°.

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